

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF NATIONAL IMAGE IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

Valiyeva Kh.R.

Assistant of the "Physical education and sports" department of Tashkent Transport University,
Independent Researcher of the Institute for Retraining and Advanced Training of Directors and
Specialists of Preschool Education Organizations

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Abstract. *The article discusses the role and significance of the concept of national image in preschool education.*

Keywords: *national model of education, image phenomenon, management image, national image of the preschool education system, national image of the preschool education organization.*

Research on improving the management skills of leaders in managing the national image of preschool education organizations worldwide focuses on enhancing leadership competencies, managing the national image of educational institutions, and studying new approaches to improving the quality of education. Studies conducted in the U.S., Finland, and other countries highlight the importance of implementing high-quality programs in preschool education. These programs include pedagogical approaches and teaching methods that create better experiences for children and families. Similarly, systematic efforts are being made in Europe, Asia and America to explore various approaches to teaching and education management. These studies play a crucial role in developing management skills in leaders and building a reliable and strong image for preschool education organizations in the global education system. As a result, they contribute to creating a better educational environment for children and raising the importance of education in society.

In our country, the education system, especially preschool education, is of vital importance for children's development and their future personalities. Preschool education institutions play a significant role in preparing children for school and nurturing them. Therefore, the national image and trustworthy reputation of preschool education organizations are essential factors in improving the quality of education. The management skills of leaders should foster a positive environment, attract qualified teaching staff, and influence children's personal development. Managing the national image of preschool education organizations depends on the capabilities and strategies of their leaders. Hence, developing effective mechanisms to enhance leaders' management skills is a pressing task.

In preschool education, the concept of "national image" refers to instilling Uzbek culture, traditions, and values in children, familiarizing them with their nation's history, language, and customs. This concept plays a crucial role in the social, cultural, and psychological development of children within the preschool education system. One of the key aspects of forming a national image is teaching national culture.

“The national model of education in Uzbekistan is a comprehensive set of theoretical-methodological and practical-pedagogical approaches aimed at fundamentally reforming the education system based on renewed, sound pedagogical thinking. It seeks to raise the intellectual, spiritual, and moral levels of specialists trained in educational institutions to the standards of

developed countries. The national model of education envisions ensuring that an intellectually and morally well-rounded individual fully realizes their creative potential” [1].

“Image is a complex socio-psychological concept that holds significant importance in modern society. It directly affects not only how a person is perceived but also their status in society and the 'persona' constructed around them. Analyzing this concept requires an interdisciplinary approach. Moreover, in today's era of advanced digital technologies and social networks, the formation and management of personal and corporate images have become even more relevant. Therefore, this article focuses on discussing the socio-psychological characteristics of image, its formation, and its role in society” [2].

The word “image” is derived from the French term *image*, meaning “representation” or “picture,” which, in turn, originates from the Latin word *imago*, also meaning “figure,” “form,” or “image.” The term entered English from French and later spread to other languages. An image (in English, *image* – form, picture) is a synthetic representation that embodies information about a specific person, organization, or other social object in people's minds and influences social behavior. Today, the concept of “image” refers to the external appearance of individuals, organizations, or products, as well as the overall perception of how they are presented to others. As a result, the term is widely used in various fields, including psychology, marketing, media, and political science.

The English scholar F. Jenkins, a proponent of the functional approach to image, proposes the following types of images:

Mirror Image – the image reflecting one’s perception of themselves.

Current Image – the image shaped by external perceptions.

Desired Image – the image representing what an individual aspires to become.

Corporate Image – the overall image of an organization, not limited to individual departments or results.

Multiple Images – an image formed when several independent structures exist instead of a single corporation.

There is also a contextual approach to the concept of image. This approach emphasizes that an image should have a cohesive and coordinated nature, considering the conditions necessary for its realization, and its various aspects should not contradict each other. According to the English scholar E. Simpson, when discussing personal image, she classifies it into three types based on the harmony between external and internal factors: self-image, perceived image, and required image.

Self-image stems from past experiences and reflects one's current state of self-respect and confidence.

Perceived image is how others view us.

Required image refers to the specific characteristics demanded by certain professions or roles. In some cases, clothing helps convey this image. Military uniforms, judicial robes, and royal crowns are all indicators of the roles an individual play.

Some researchers propose charismatic image as a separate category. The concept of charisma and the charismatic leader was introduced into academic discourse by one of the founders of sociology, Max Weber.

Individuals can "project" onto this image whatever qualities they believe in. Typically, the less information people have about a person, the more influential that person appears in their eyes. Depending on different spheres of activity and social contexts where the image is formed, various

types of images exist, such as political image (and politicians' images), business image, organizational image, and national image. These images differ in content, formation mechanisms, and modes of expression.

Thus, the formation of an image can be integrated into a rational system of social management, as there are many untapped opportunities in this area. The importance of image in presenting oneself, one's company, or organization to partners and the public is not yet fully understood by all employees and leaders. Many still operate in outdated ways, resulting in losses in competitive environments.

In conclusion, the concept of image is one of the most critical gnoseological issues, with many theoretical, practical, and technological challenges depending on its resolution. Below, we will examine the concept of managerial image.

Managerial image refers to the perception and representation of an organization formed in the public eye, particularly among employees and clients, based on the leadership's interactions, work processes, and organizational culture. The managerial image is shaped by leaders' leadership styles, abilities, personal traits, and management strategies.

In preschool education, the national image is the process of instilling the culture, traditions, customs, and values of Uzbek people in children's minds. This process aims to teach children about their nation's history, language, and culture, preparing them for social life, fostering self-awareness, and enhancing respect for their heritage. The formation of a national image is reflected in curricula, pedagogical activities, and interactions with children, highlighting the uniqueness, cultural heritage, and rich history of Uzbek nation.

The national image of a preschool education institution is a socially accepted image created with consideration for Uzbek national values and culture. This image encompasses qualities and values inherent to Uzbek people and is reflected in interactions among children, parents, teachers, and the broader community.

Based on the analysis of the above sources, it can be concluded that the core of the managerial image in preschool education institutions lies in the leader's leadership style, organizational culture, management strategies, relationships with staff, and engagement with the community. Developing a high-quality managerial image is crucial for enhancing the reputation of preschool education institutions and achieving their goals.

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